

PECULIARITIES IN STUDYING WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI IN LITERATURE EDUCATION

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***Annotation:** Some problems in the teaching of Alisher Navoi's works and the proposed interactive methods to provide their solutions, as well as the methodological basis and peculiarities of the study of Navoi's works are discussed. Recommendations for the development of effective methods in the study of Navoi's work and their application in the educational process are set out. There are also recommendations for working with a dictionary in teaching Alisher Navoi's work, understanding the subtleties of meaning of words. Opinions on historical works dedicated to Alisher Navoi and their essence are analyzed.*

***Keywords:** character, illustrative education, insert, case-study, technology, method, strategy, anogramma, proportionality, disproportion, genre, methodology*

***Аннотация:** Обсуждаются некоторые проблемы преподавания произведений Алишера Навои и предлагаемые интерактивные методы их решения, а также методологические основы и особенности изучения произведений Навои. Изложены рекомендации по разработке эффективных методов изучения творчества Навои и их применению в учебном процессе. Также есть рекомендации по работе со словарем при обучении произведениям Алишера Навои, пониманию тонкостей значения слов. Анализируются мнения об исторических произведениях, посвященных Алишету Навои, и их сущности.*

***Ключевые слова:** персонаж, иллюстративное образование, вставка, кейс-стадия, технология, метод, стратегия, анограмма, пропорциональность, асимметрия, жанр, методология*

***Annotatsiya:** Alisher Navoiy ijodini o'qitishdagi ayrim muammolar va ularning yechimlarini ta'minlash maqsadida tavsiya etilgan interfaol usullar,*

shuningdek, Navoiy ijodini o'rganishning metodologik asoslari va o'ziga xos jihatlari borasida fikr yuritilgan. Navoiy ijodini o'rganishda ta'lim jarayonida samarador usullarini ishlab chiqish va o'quv jarayonida qo'llash borasidagi tavsiyalar bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, Alisher Navoiy Ijodini o'rgatishda lug'at bilan ishlash, so'zlarning ma'no noziklilarini tushunish borasida tavsiyalar berilgan. Alisher Navoiyga bag'ishlab yozilgan tarixiy asarlar va ularning tub mohiyati borasida fikrlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: personaj, illyustrativ ta'lim, insert, keys-stadi, texnologiya, metod, strategiya, anogramma, mutanosiblik, nomutanosiblik, janr, metodik.

INTRODUCTION. The sharing of universal values in the works of Alisher Navoi's work their educational value, as well as the ideas about recommending methods considered effective in studying his work are included in this article. Different kind of methods are recommended to ease the complex processes in teaching and learning from his work.

Research methods. In this article, there is utilized cluster, anogram, sequential method and the case-study.

Results and discussion. Desired result. To use effective methods for perceiving and analyzing the content of Alisher Navoi's works.

The teaching of Alisher Navoi's works in general educational schools has not yet been methodically organized, especially through cluster. Therefore, methodical study of the poet's works novelty of the subject.

The essence of Alisher Navoi's works - first of all, a person and his role in life and his benefit to the people around him.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. Today, the lack of understanding of the linguistic features of the poet's poems in teaching the works of Alisher Navoi, and the lack of knowledge in terms of the literature shows that serious research in these areas of education is still needed. It is especially important to study the methodological aspects of studying the work of Alisher Navoi.

“The essence of life the difference between human and all living beings is his faith (iyman)”, - says Alisher Navoi.

Therefore, in the upper classes, mainly the the works of poet are taught, a series of symbolic images rich in philosophical observations invite people to think.

Within 10th and 11th grades, according to the curriculum based on the SES excerpts from Alisher Navoi’s “Saddi Iskandari” and excerpts from Khondamir’s “Makorim ul-Akhlahk” (a work dedicated to Alisher Navoi) are given.

“Spiritual storms that cannot fit into the human body in a work of art give more opportunities to express the good intentions born in the heart, " says B. Karimov literary critic, scientist, doctor of philology. [1,5] According to these thoughts of the scientist, in the works of Navoi, we can see inner world of the poet the feelings of the heart burned with the grief of the nation and the motherland. Therefore, instilling these aspects into souls of students in teaching creativity is the most important task of today's teacher.

Using the “Anogram” method based on impressions of Navoi’s works gives good result. Find the mismatching given names. Which ones did not give any opinion about Navoi?

“Among the answers to the question based on the cluster method Sakkoki did not give any description to Alisher Navoi. On the other hand, in “Majolis un-Nafois”, Navoi himself gave information about Sakkoki.

In fact, the student, who is just growing up as a person, should be able to feel the experiences of his own psyche during the process of reading and studying any artistic work.

In this connection, integrity or closeness can call him to evaluate the views and actions of the characters of the work.

In literature education there is a concept explanatory-illustrative education. When explaining this field, more attention is paid to visuality.

In this case, in order to remember information from the textbook, It is possible to remember information based on visual aids.

For instance, in the 10th grade literature textbook AlisherNavoi's evaluations of famous scholarships and historians. [2,80] or in the 11th grade literature textbook, the passage from Saddi Iskandari's epic and the information related to the epic can be recommended in order to learn the following methods. [3,124] Also based on the impressions from Navoi's works another "Anogram" method can be used. Find the mismatching given names. Which ones did not give any opinion about Navoi?

Based on 10th grade literature textbook.

Or we invite the following drawing in order to strengthen theoretical knowledge.

Which information does not belong to the epic “Saddi Iskandari”?

“It can be strengthen theme by using “Sequential method”.

№	Pictures	Name of the work
1.		“Munshaot”
2.		“Sabbai Sayyor”
3.		“Farkhad and Shirin”
4.		“Layli and Majnun”
5.		“Lison ut-tair”

6.		“Khamsat ut-mutahirin”
7.		“Saddi Iskandary
8.		“Sabbai Sayyor”
9.		“Hayrat ul-abror”
10.		“Mezon ul avzon”

Based on the same method, it is also possible to assign the task of placing Khamsa’s epics.

Using the technology of “Insert” strategy, th class is divided into groups and names are chosen for them. For example, They can be named with the heroes of “Khamsa” epic. Each student should give two pieces of information about the topic

(but the answers must not be repeated). At the end information is collected. Information written down to the paper or board. Finally main text is given to the pupils, explanations are summarized and tasks are given.

Farkhad

Iskandar

1. Farkhod Do not greedy for wealth

1. Iskandar Do not like wealth

2. Talented thirst for knowledge

2. Talented intelligent

It is important to learn the theme deeply based on 'Case study' technology. The meaning of this method is versatile and teaches logical thinking.

It can be seen that systematically conducting the process of improving educational efficiency and ensuring consistency in order to learn and improve Alisher Navoi's creativity will give good results. Because Fiction is a unique means and the source of understanding the world. Any student who can perceive works of art, draw logical conclusions from them and feel the artistry of the poet can undoubtedly create only good things in life. They can spread the life of their world to those around them and they can make many people enjoy their goodness.

Each Alisher Navoi's masterpiece (regardless of genre) has collected the colors of this beautiful world. It is inevitable that a person who enjoys this will strive for perfection. In this way, it is important that the teachers holds the candle high.

Apparently, in the teaching process of Alisher Navoi's work, the most important aspect is the wide range of information, working with the dictionaries in the text, bringing the originality of the poet's works into the souls of the young generation and increasing effectiveness of education.

Methodologically, based on the sequence of the topics, the use of interactive methods based on new pedagogical technologies has a great impact on the quality and effectiveness of education.

Therefore, perceiving the poet's works with all their content and essence forms the spirit of respect and reverence for universal human values in students.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION. The practical results of the work are the followings:

- to analyze the pedagogical psychological feature of bringing up students in the spirit of a perfect human being in the process of literary education;
- a model of the perfect human being has been developed in the literature lessons which is reflected in the work of Alisher Navoi;
- the content and factors of educating students in the spirit of a perfect human being are revealed in the system of literary education.

The indicators of Alisher Navoi's view of the spirit of the perfect human being has been improved in terms of didactic, methodological, and basic competencies.

CONCLUSIONS. There is given recommendations as examples of themes Alisher Navoi's works within 10th and 11th grades.

In this case, the efficiency of using interactive methods is maintained in order to remember information well.

The goal of improving theoretical knowledge through various methods is established.

The effectiveness of methods and the importance of working with pictures are shown.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In the teaching process of classical literature, as well as in the study of the works of Alisher Navoi, interactive methods should be chosen based on the level of difficulty of the topic.
2. Methods will be recommended according to the complexity and abundance of information.
3. In the process of teaching the works of Alisher Navoi, they should recognize the attitude of the thinker to universal or global values.
4. The issue of national values and mother tongue should not be overlooked.

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